

Effect of sources and timing of nitrogen application on the grain yield of rice variety Rasi (IET 1444). Mandya, India, 1979 summer.

Treatments ^a B - T - PI	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./m ² x 100)	1000-grain wt (g)
0 - 0 - 0	3.0	260	161	20
60 - 0 - 0	5.4	342	233	22
30 - 0 - 30	4.6	340	217	23
30 - 30 - 0	5.2	332	245	21
0 - 30 - 30	3.4	270	204	21
60 ^{nc} 0 - 0	4.6	302	209	20
60 ^{fym} 0 - 0	3.1	228	163	19
60 ^{SG1} 0 - 0	6.1	373	294	20
60 ^{SG2} 0 - 0	5.6	394	298	21
60 ^{GC} 0 - 0	6.3	413	304	22
CD (0.05):	0.7	-	-	-

^aB = basal; T = tillering; PI = panicle initiation; nc = urea blended with neem cake; fym = farmyard manure enriched with urea; SG1 = supergranule (1-g size); SG2 = supergranule (2-g size); GC = granulated compost.

granules gave the highest grain yields (see table). High panicle production and high grain number accounted for the increased yield. Urea blended with neem cake (using coal tar) and farmyard manure

enriched with urea did not give superior performance. The lack of a clear response to split application could have been caused by the short growth duration (120 days) of the test variety. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Rice ratoon crop management in hilly regions of Karnataka, India

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Ratoon cropping might increase rice production without an increase in land area. Reports of good ratoon crop yields in the hilly regions of Karnataka and farmers' acceptance of ratoon cropping have encouraged researchers to evaluate the potential for increasing and stabilizing rice ratoon yields and to identify optimum management practices. A preliminary study on ratoon cropping was therefore undertaken in a farmer's field.

Two replicated experiments were

conducted to determine the effect of cutting time and cutting height. A third experiment continued the yield performance study conducted in 1978. All studies were conducted with the stubble of the 1978 wet season harvest at Sringeri, Chikmaglore District, which is representative of the hilly rice region. In the first experiment cutting time was fixed at 35, 40, and 45 days after 50% flowering (40 days is the normal harvest time). The net plot size was 10 m² with 3 replications in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The main crop seeded on 30 June and cultivated with farmers' practices was cut, leaving a stubble height of 13 cm on 13, 18, and 23 December. The entire experimental area was topdressed with 50 kg urea/ha

Table 1. Effects of cutting time after 50% flowering and cutting height of the main crop on the grain yield of the ratoon crop of variety Intan.

Days after 50% flowering	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Cutting ht (cm) from ground	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
30	3.0	8	2.8
35	3.1	13	2.9
40	3.1	18	2.6

^aCV: 13%. ^bCV: 21%.

(44% N) 30 days after the second treatment (18 Jan 79). In the second experiment, cutting heights were 8, 13, and 18 cm above the ground, and a RCBD was replicated 4 times. The net plot size was a direct-seeded 2-m row. The main crop seeded on 30 June and managed with farmers' practices was cut on 23 December 1978 and topdressed with 50 kg urea/ha 30 days later. The third experiment, located at Balehonnur, repeated the 1977 experiment.

The main crop seeded on 23 June 1978 was cut on 9 December and the ratoon was topdressed 40 days later at 40 kg urea/ha. The ratoon was harvested on 21 April 1979. The other practices followed were local ones. All 3 experimental crops lost an estimated 35% to birds (there were no rice plots around the experiments).

Neither the cutting time nor the cutting height influenced grain yield (Table 1). A 5-day interval after harvest seems to be too short to cause significant yield differences because the main and ratoon crops have long growth durations (171 and 130 days). Longer cutting intervals might cause significant differences. Similarly, the yield differences attributable to cutting height were not significant, but treatments differing by 10 cm or more might produce large differences. With the late-maturing variety Intan, minor differences in cutting time and height of the main crop appear to have no significant influence on yield.

Table 2. Yield data of main (MC) and ratoon crops (RC) of Intan at Balehonnur, Karnataka, India, 1978-79, at different fertility levels.

MC treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Yield of RC (% of MC)
	MC	RC	
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	4.2	2.1	50
N ₄₀ P ₀ K ₀	5.2	2.6	50
N ₈₀ P ₀ K ₀	5.3	2.1	51
N ₁₂₀ P ₀ K ₀	5.9	2.5	42
N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₀	5.3	2.7	51
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₀	5.7	2.8	49
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₀	6.0	2.9	48
N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₂₀	5.4	2.8	52
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀	5.7	2.8	49
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	5.7	3.5	61
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₄₀	6.1	3.4	56
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₄₀ + Zn	6.2	3.1	50
Mean	5.6	2.8	50

The ratoon crop yields in the third experiment were attractive: an average of 2.9 t/ha ranging from 50 to 60% of

the main crop. But their yields were much lower than those of 1977–78. Bird damage contributed to the

discrepancy to some extent. The factors that cause such high yield fluctuations should be further investigated. ■

Announcements

Training course on techniques in bioproductivity and photosynthesis offered in Yugoslavia

A course of practical instruction in techniques used in bioproductivity and photosynthesis will be offered in Belgrade, Yugoslavia, 22 August – 6 September 1980. The following topics will be covered:

- biofuels and energy balances
- field photosynthesis measurements
- plant photosynthetic characteristics
- carbon assimilation and metabolism
- cell and chloroplast reactions, and
- nitrogen metabolism.

Sponsors of the course are the United Nations Environment Programme and the Maize Research Institute, Belgrade.

Methods applicable to field and

laboratory studies will be presented in a form suitable for young scientists (minimum qualifications, M.Sc. or equivalent) from developing countries. Instruction will be in English.

Participants will be expected to attend the 5th International Congress on Photosynthesis in Kallithea, near Thessaloniki in northern Greece (close to Belgrade) from 7-13 September 1980 (that program is relevant to the subject matter of the training course). Registration will be provided; travel and accommodation support will be negotiated.

Applications are invited and should arrive by 1 May 1980. Applicants will not be considered unless the following information is provided: 1) a detailed curriculum vitae, 2) a brief description

of present and future research and its relevance to the program, and 3) a letter of support from their supervisors (this is essential).

Limited funds for travel and local accommodation will be available. Candidates are also urged to apply to national and international agencies for support.

The organizing committee consists of J. A. Berry, Stanford; J. Coombs, Reading; D. O. Hall, London; and Z. Vucinic, Belgrade.

Apply to:

Coordinator,
UNEP Study Group
University of London King's College
68 Half Moon Lane
London SE24 9JF, U.K.

IRRI will release publication printing negatives

The main purpose of IRRI publications is wide dissemination of information on rice research and production to scientists, educators, and extension specialists.

To broaden that information dissemination, IRRI has initiated a new policy. We will provide duplicate printing negatives of selected IRRI publications to any agricultural developmental organization or publishing company in a developing nation that wishes to reprint IRRI volumes in that country.

When IRRI publishes a book the vast majority of publication costs — editing, typesetting, artwork, layout, and design — are “captured” on the offset printing negatives. Local organizations can use duplicate negatives to print their own volumes of IRRI publications at a cost even much lower than direct purchase from IRRI.

IRRI will release printing negatives

under these conditions:

1. IRRI will release negatives only to organizations in developing nations.

2. No organization will sell the reprinted IRRI publications outside its own country.

3. Reprinted IRRI publications should not be priced higher than the IRRI discounted price for developing nations (which represents only typesetting, negative, paper, and printing expenses).

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a. For the title page, IRRI will provide a new negative that includes the phrase *This publication was reprinted with the permission of the International Rice Research Institute.*

b. For the cover, the requesting organization is free to either order

duplicate IRRI printing negatives, or to design and print its own cover (but IRRI must be recognized on the cover as the originator of the volume).

5. The requesting organization is free to determine the paper stock and printing process to be used.

6. The requesting organization will reimburse IRRI for the negative reproduction costs, and for shipping charges (at 1979 prices, about US\$300 for a typical 200-page publication).

The principle of the new printing policy is similar to that of the IRRI Farm Machinery Development Program; when IRRI engineers design a new farm machine, they release the blueprints — free — to qualified organizations or commercial firms in the developing nations that want to manufacture it.

We hope that the new policy will increase the dissemination of rice information and lower its cost. It should save foreign exchange in the developing nations, and help build local capacity for